

Supplement. STROBE reporting checklist (cross-sectional studies)

Reporting follows the STROBE statement for cross-sectional studies (von Elm E, et al. *Lancet*. 2007;370:1453-1457). Item text is abbreviated; locations refer to sections of the main manuscript.

Item	Recommendation	Reported in
1a	Study design indicated by a common term in title or abstract	Abstract (cross-sectional analysis); Methods, Study design and reporting
1b	Informative, balanced abstract summary	Abstract
2	Background and rationale	Introduction, paragraphs 1-3
3	Objectives and prespecified hypotheses	Introduction, final paragraph; pre-specified determinant pairs in Methods, Explainability
4	Key elements of study design, stated early	Methods, Study design and reporting
5	Setting, locations, and relevant dates	Methods, Data source and study population; Survey year (2024 cycle)
6a	Eligibility criteria, sources, and selection of participants	Methods, Data source and study population
7	Clearly defined outcomes, exposures, and predictors	Methods, Outcome; Predictors

Item	Recommendation	Reported in
8	Sources of data and methods of assessment for each variable	Methods, Outcome (<code>_CRCREC3</code>); Predictors (BRFSS items); variable crosswalk in repository
9	Efforts to address sources of bias	Methods, Missing data and survey weights (design-based inference, in-fold preprocessing to prevent leakage); Discussion, Strengths and limitations (self-report bias)
10	How study size was arrived at	Methods, Data source and study population (full eligible sample analyzed)
11	Handling of quantitative variables	Methods, Prediction models (age modeled with a restricted cubic spline); income and education analyzed as ordered categories
12a	Statistical methods, including control of confounding	Methods, Prediction models; Validation and performance
12b	Methods to examine subgroups and interactions	Methods, Explainability (product-term interaction tests); Validation (equity audit)
12c	How missing data were addressed	Methods, Missing data and survey weights

Item	Recommendation	Reported in
12d	Methods accounting for sampling strategy	Methods, Missing data and survey weights (design-based inference: strata, primary sampling units, weights)
12e	Sensitivity analyses	Methods, Validation and performance (unweighted refit; never-screened vs overdue decomposition)
13a	Numbers of individuals at each stage	Results, Sample and outcome; analytic flow in repository
13b	Reasons for non-participation or exclusion	Methods, Missing data and survey weights (missing outcome or non-positive weight excluded)
13c	Flow diagram	Participant-flow file in repository
14a	Characteristics of participants	Results, Sample characteristics (Table 1)
14b	Number of participants with missing data per variable	Methods, Missing data and survey weights (in-fold imputation); Discussion, Strengths and limitations (reduced-coverage items)

Item	Recommendation	Reported in
15	Outcome events or summary measures	Results, Sample and outcome (weighted delay prevalence)
16a	Estimates and their precision (confidence intervals)	Results, Model performance; Determinants and their interactions (design-based 95% CIs)
16b	Category boundaries when variables were categorized	Results, Equity across social groups (income bands); Table 1
16c	Relative to absolute risk translation	Model outputs are calibrated absolute risks (Results, Model performance)
17	Other analyses (subgroups, interactions, sensitivity)	Results, Determinants and their interactions; Equity across social groups; Outcome decomposition and sensitivity analyses
18	Key results with reference to objectives	Discussion, Principal findings
19	Limitations, with direction and magnitude of bias	Discussion, Strengths and limitations
20	Cautious overall interpretation	Discussion, Interpretation and mechanisms; Comparison with prior work

Item	Recommendation	Reported in
21	Generalizability	Discussion, Strengths and limitations (internal validation; transportability)
22	Funding	Title page, Funding statement